

MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES IN TEACHING LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *A large part of the written sources focused on differentiation and motivation. They stressed using a variety of teaching methods, different materials and types of tasks as well as incorporating the learners. According to the written sources it is important to help learners improve their own learning techniques and develop their cooperation and collaboration with their peers. This is also something that the teachers mention, as they think small groups work and peer work is beneficial for the learners.*

Key words: *cooperation and collaboration, technique, comprehension, lexical clues, mental lexicon, strong semantic links, connection*

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Why do we teach foreign languages in schools? Clearly, not simply for the learner to be able to write to a foreign pen friend, to be able to calculate his income tax or understand his domestic fuse-box, though these are all practical by-products of the learning process. The major areas of the school curriculum are the instruments by which the individual grows into a more secure, more contributory, more total member of society. Similarly, the teaching of history is all about ourselves in relationship to other people in other times: now in relation to then. This achievement of perspective, this breaking of parochial boundaries, the relating to other people, places, things and events is no less applicable to foreign language teaching. By learning a foreign language, we see our own in perspective, we recognize that there are other ways of saying things, other ways of thinking, other patterns of emphasis.

So, the teacher leads and guides the students through the text that they arrive at sound interpretations which are properly justified. There was a significant correlation between reading comprehension and learners' awareness of unknown DT words. It can be argued, therefore, that deceptive transparency is indeed a factor which has an effect on comprehension.

As mentioned before, the correlation between awareness of DT words and reading scores was, significant at level A1, though correlations do not show cause-effect relationships between the variables, they do indicate the degree of common variance. In our case, it seems that about variance in reading could be accounted for by the degree of awareness of DT words. When a foreign learner does not understand a word in the text, he has the following options: ignore it (if he considers it unimportant), look it up in a dictionary, ask someone who knows its meaning, or try to guess it from con-text. Many researchers of reading and pedagogues have emphasized the importance of guessing as a strategy of successful reading presupposes

awareness, on the part of the learner, that he is facing an unknown word¹. If such awareness is not there, no attempt is made to infer the missing meaning. This is precisely the case with deceptively transparent words.

“It is well known that wisdom and spirit of the nation are shown in the traditions and customs of the country, especially in its folklore. Folklore is the most mysterious and unusual genre of children’s literature. And one of the most popular parts of folklore is a fairytale. It has got an exciting plot, brave characters and a happy ending that really attracts readers”². The learner thinks he knows then and assigns the wrong meaning to them, distorting the immediate context on this way. The result was the following: 'Instead of living natural life, natural behavior, females and children find many different forms of life.' One might wonder about the lack of syntactic resemblance between the original and the misinterpreted sentences. Such incongruences in sentence structure show that students are willing to rely on lexical clues more than on syntactic ones; they are even prepared to impose a sentence structure on the idea they have already arrived at via lexis. If the learner had recognized 'nurture, fend, leave' as unknown words in the given example, he might have looked up or guessed their meaning and arrived at a different interpretation.

The study did not attempt to investigate the characteristics of the mental lexicon. However, some of the errors caused by DT words can provide some information about the organization of L2 words in the memory. Investigations have indicated that while in the native speaker's mental lexicon there are strong semantic links between the words, the connections between words in additional languages are primarily phonological³.

Another interesting issue that has been debated is whether words composed of root and affixes are stored as single units or whether the stems and affixes are stored separately. Errors in the words with a deceptively morphological structure seem to support the latter (lexical decompositions hypothesis). The learner might store the prefix 'dis-' separately and therefore interpret 'discourse' as 'without direction', combining what looks like two separate units of meaning. Also the confusions of morphological forms (industrial/industrious, economic/economical) might result from storing the suffixes separately and substituting one by another.

The case study suggested an additional psychological condition for learning words through reading: the importance of a wide and free choice of books⁴. The procedure of choosing and "grading" books mentioned before contributed considerably to the motivation of the children to read the selected book and probably as well to their retention of the content. The

¹ Ainslie, Susan. (1994). *Mixed Ability Teaching: Meeting Learners' Needs. Network 3: Teaching Language to Adults*. London: Centre for Information on Language Teaching and Research.

² Khalilova Sh.J. (2022) Common similarities and Difficulties of Uzbek and English fairy tales. European journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education. Volume 2/Issue 1/ ISSN:2795-8612

³ Baker, Joanna. (2000). *The English language teacher's handbook: how to teach large classes with few resources*. New York: Continuum; London: Cassel.

⁴ Berry, Eve and Williams, Molly. (1992). *Teaching Strategies for Multilevel ESL classes. Facilitator's Guide*. Oregon: Clackamas Community College.

study indicated that this also brought about a good retention of a number of words occurring in important passages of the books. Finally, it was remarkable that the amount of interest in the subject appeared to prevail over the degree of difficulty of the language. This phenomenon and the importance of a free and wide choice was also found in a study concerning the relations between leisure reading in the mother tongue and reading English by Toussaint-Dekker.

As children see concepts reflected in the world around them, they become enthusiastic and engaged learners. In this work you will find activities to foster children's social and emotional development, build language and literacy skills, and develop an understanding of math concepts. You will also find science activities that strengthen children's observation and reasoning skills, music and movement activities that get everyone involved, and group art activities that inspire creativity and cooperation. An Early Childhood Standards Correlation Chart is included to help you quickly identify activities that focus on a specific skill. For instance, the following activities will be useful for using in interactive classes.

Alphabetical Toss. Materials. Large balls

Choose a letter to begin the game, such as the letter *b*. Stand in a circle and toss a ball to a child, saying a word that begins with the letter *b*, such as the word *bat*. That child then throws the ball to another child and says another word that begins with letter *b*, such as the word *baseball*. Continue around the circle. As each child catches the ball, he or she says a word that begins with the chosen letter. As an alternative, this activity can be done in pairs or in small groups. To challenge children even more, ask them to name, in order, a word for each letter of the alphabet. For younger children: Invite pairs of children to roll or toss the balls back and forth, emphasizing the *b* sounds in the words *ball* and *bounce*.

A bowl of Jelly. Materials. None

Invite children to move like things that begin with the letter *j*. First ask children what words they can think of that begin with the letter *j*. They may say words such as *jelly*, *jack-in-the-box*, *jumping jacks*, or *jaguar*. Then invite children to move like the letter *j*!

Monkey shines. Motor Skills. Materials None

M is for *monkey*! Invite children to act like monkeys—jump on chairs, hop around, swing, make monkey sounds, and so on. If possible, place mats on the floor for children to bounce on. Then ask children if they can think of other animals that begin with the letter *m* (mouse, moose, mole). Children can act out these animals, as well.

A quantitative approach of lexical richness and variety can offer a macro-picture on the learner's lexicon. In the lexicometric and stylostistical literature a variety of measures has been proposed for spelling out the lexical characteristics of a written and spoken text. The lexical variety or richness of a text is usually defined as a function of the number of types (*V*) in relation to the number of tokens (*N*). The number of tokens constitutes the text length. For the words used by our informants, a set of 11 lexical measures has been selected originally, mainly based on Menard.

In any lexical study on richness and variety information should be provided about the operationalization of basic categories such as word tokens, word forms, lemmas or other basic

counting units. Operationalization problems will be not discussed here. More information can be found in Breeder et al.

The steps taken in the operationalization of the lexical data base can be summarized as follows:

First, concordance lists are made which give the word forms used by the learner in alphabetical order, together with the contexts and the frequency of the word forms.

Next the list of word forms is 'cleaned up' by excluding, for instance, false word starts, and is converted into a list of word tokens; a word form is defined as a class of identical word tokens.

Finally, the word forms are coded and stored in the form of records in which a fixed number of fields specifies the word form, the word class, the hypothesized learner meaning, the lemma, the frequency, and the place of occurrence (informant, cycle, encounter, activity). The lemma field contains dictionary entries of the target language.

Excluded from the data base are false word starts, but included are word repeats. They are included because repeats can be viewed as a determining property of spontaneous speech in general and of the spontaneous speech of language learners in particular. These repeats contain self-repeats as well as other repeats (e.g., imitations of the native speaker/interlocutor). Every transcript of an activity has a specific number of different word types. The frequency of a word type is the sum of the frequencies of the word forms belonging to that word type. The total frequency of the word types in a text or the number of tokens is the sum of the frequencies of all word types together. A word type is defined as the combination of the entry in the lemma field and the grammatical word class code. Any mismatch between these elements implies that the records in question contain different word types. For instance, 'werk' (work) coded as a noun is not the same word type as 'werk' (work) coded as a verb. As a consequence, one-word type may enclose different word forms.

Teachers can make the article a lot more approachable if they get the learners to work on some aspects of the comprehension before they see the whole article. There are a number of different ways you can reveal part of the article and, in the same process, pre-teach some of the ideas in the article. Good examples of this are 'Let's find out what you know already' (see lessons that require little or no preparation), 'Before you read true or false' or 'Matching split sentence halves' (see providing added value). This, incidentally, makes the article more interesting for everyone, because by slowly revealing a bit of the article at a time, you are keeping your students guessing and whetting their appetites for the whole article at the same time! Also getting the learners to work with some of the key lexis in the article before they see it will make it a lot easier and more satisfying for them to read. Some good examples of this are 'Group work on key vocabulary' (see lessons that require little or no preparation), 'Matching words, expressions or word partnerships to definitions' or 'Focusing on a lexical area' (see lessons that provide added value).

Asking questions: Often teacher can explain, or draw attention to, difficult vocabulary in reading comprehension questions. They can ask specific questions to find out if learners have understood a particular point, or they can ask broad questions for them to discuss, where many different answers are possible.

Here are some examples of specific questions (based on the cut article):

- 1 What is a dead duck?
 - 2 What does “cutting the cord” mean in this article?
 - 3 What other “handy features” can you have on a mobile phone?
 - 4 How can fixed-mobile convergence give consumers the best of both worlds?
- You can also ask specific questions like:
- 5 How can integrated operators save money with fixed mobile convergence?

Learners will probably have to understand what “integrated operators” means in order to answer the question. But if their answer is “They can save money by merging network infrastructures and doing away with separate fixed and mobile divisions.” i.e. a verbatim quotation from the article which does indeed answer the question – it still does not indicate to you that they have understood any of the words in their answer! It is also important for learners to practice asking questions themselves. So, exercises that make learners ask questions are extremely valuable. The written sources and the teachers on the same type of difficulties with mixed-ability classes it is hard to keep everyone’s attention, hard to motivate everyone. The teacher feels that he/she does not have enough time to help all learners, the learners can be easily bored, and planning the lesson to meet all of them. It is important for the teacher working in a mixed ability class to create a good atmosphere where the students feel secure, can voice their opinions and ask questions without feeling anxious. One of the most important things for the teacher to aim for is to be clear and structured, according to the teachers.

The special teacher did not agree with the written sources opinions on this as she did not find it necessary at all. She only works systematically and in a structured way with each text to create routines, and the weaker learners work really well with this and do improve.

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